

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

AN EFFICIENT METHOD FOR THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF FIFTH ORDER INITIAL VALUE PROBLEMS

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an efficient numerical method to solve fifth order initial value problems. Analysis proves that the proposed method have at least quadratic convergence. Numerical results confirm the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: *Initial Value Problems, Taylor series, Maximum Absolute Error, Approximation, Lipschitz condition.*

1. Introduction

An efficient method for solving second order initial value problems has been proposed by P. K. Pandey and Archana Yadav in [7] and for third and fourth order initial value problems by the authors in [5, 6].

In this paper, we study an effective numerical technique based on Taylor series approximation to solve fifth order initial value problems (IVPs) of the following type :

$$u^V = f(x, u, u', u'', u''', u^{IV}), a \leq x \leq b, \quad (1.1)$$

subject to the initial conditions

$$u(a) = \alpha_0, u'(a) = \alpha_1, u''(a) = \alpha_2, u'''(a) = \alpha_3, u^{IV}(a) = \alpha_4 \quad (1.2)$$

where the function f is continuous in $[a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$.

We assume that f satisfies a Lipschitz condition in a convex domain D of $[a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$ so that above problem 1.1 with 1.2 possesses a unique solution [1, 2, 3].

To find an approximation to the solution of the above problem, we discretize

the domain $[a, b]$ into N equal subintervals each of size $h = \frac{b-a}{N}$:

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N-1} < x_N = b \quad (1.3)$$

where the nodes are given by $x_i = a + ih, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

We denote by $u(x)$, the true solution of the above problem in $[a, b]$ and by $u_i, u'_i, u''_i, u'''_i, u^{IV}_i$ the approximations to the true solution and its derivatives $u(x_i), u'(x_i), u''(x_i), u'''(x_i), u^{IV}(x_i)$ respectively in this order for each $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$. We also denote f_i for the approximate value of

$$f(x_i, u(x_i), u'(x_i), u''(x_i), u'''(x_i), u^{IV}(x_i)). \quad (1.4)$$

This article is arranged in the following order. In section 2, we derive the method and discuss its convergence. In section 3, we illustrate the method with examples.

2. The Derivation of the Scheme and Convergence Analysis

Choose and fix a real number :

$$a \neq -1.$$

We define the scheme :

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{u_{i+1}} &= u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u'''_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u^{IV}_i + c_1h^5u_i^V + c_2h^6u_i^{VI} \\ \overline{u'_{i+1}} &= u'_i + hu''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u'''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u_i^V + c_1h^5u_i^{VI} \\ \overline{u''_{i+1}} &= u''_i + hu'''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u_i^V + c_1h^4u_i^{VI} \\ \overline{u'''_{i+1}} &= u'''_i + hu^{IV}_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i^V + c_1h^3u_i^{VI} \end{aligned}$$

$$\overline{u_{i+1}^{IV}} = u_i^{IV} + hu_i^V + c_1 h^2 u_i^{VI} \quad (2.1)$$

We find $a_0, b_0, c_0, d_0, e_0, c_1, c_2$ so that

$$u_{i+1} = a_0(\overline{u_{i+1}} + au_i) + b_0h(\overline{u_{i+1}'} + au_i') + c_0h^2(\overline{u_{i+1}''} + au_i'') + d_0h^3(\overline{u_{i+1}'''} + au_i''') + e_0h^4(\overline{u_{i+1}^{IV}} + au_i^{IV})$$

Using Taylor series on the left hand side

$$\begin{aligned} u_{i+1} &= u_i + hu_i' + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i'' + \frac{h^3}{3!}u_i''' + \frac{h^4}{4!}u_i^{IV} + \frac{h^5}{5!}u_i^V + \frac{h^6}{6!}u_i^{VI} + O(h^7) \\ &= a_0 \left(u_i + hu_i' + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i'' + \frac{h^3}{6}u_i''' + \frac{h^4}{24}u_i^{IV} + c_1h^5u_i^V + c_2h^6u_i^{VI} + au_i \right) \\ &\quad + b_0h \left(u_i' + hu_i'' + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i''' + \frac{h^3}{6}u_i^{IV} + \frac{h^4}{24}u_i^V + c_1h^5u_i^{VI} + au_i' \right) \\ &\quad + c_0h^2 \left(u_i'' + hu_i''' + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i^{IV} + \frac{h^3}{6}u_i^V + c_1h^4u_i^{VI} + au_i'' \right) \\ &\quad + d_0h^3 \left(u_i''' + hu_i^{IV} + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i^V + c_1h^3u_i^{VI} + au_i''' \right) \\ &\quad + e_0h^4(u_i^{IV} + hu_i^V + c_1h^2u_i^{VI} + au_i^{IV}) \quad (2.2) \end{aligned}$$

Truncating the series and equating the corresponding coefficients of

$$u_i, hu_i', h^2u_i'', h^3u_i''', h^4u_i^{IV}, h^5u_i^V, h^6u_i^{VI}$$

on both the sides, we get

$$\begin{aligned} aa_0 + a_0 &= 1 \\ ab_0 + b_0 + a_0 &= 1 \\ ac_0 + c_0 + b_0 + \frac{a_0}{2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\ ad_0 + d_0 + c_0 + \frac{b_0}{2} + \frac{a_0}{6} &= \frac{1}{6} \\ ae_0 + e_0 + d_0 + \frac{c_0}{2} + \frac{b_0}{6} + \frac{a_0}{24} &= \frac{1}{24} \\ e_0 + \frac{d_0}{2} + a_0c_1 + \frac{c_0}{6} + \frac{b_0}{24} &= \frac{1}{120} \\ c_1e_0 + c_1d_0 + a_0c_2 + c_0c_1 + b_0c_1 &= \frac{1}{720} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Solving these, we get

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \quad a_0 &= \frac{1}{(1+a)} \\ 2 \quad b_0 &= \frac{a}{(1+a)^2} \\ 3 \quad c_0 &= \frac{a(a-1)}{2(1+a)^3} \\ 4 \quad d_0 &= \frac{a(a^2-4a+1)}{6(a+1)^4} \\ 5 \quad e_0 &= \frac{(a-1)a(a^2-10a+1)}{24(a+1)^5} \\ 6 \quad c_1 &= \frac{(a^5-25a^4+70a^3-20a^2+5a+1)}{120(a+1)^4} \\ 7 \quad c_2 &= -\frac{(37a^9-1000a^8+1260a^7+1654a^6+2236a^5-288a^4-280a^3-10a^2-21a-4)}{2880(a+1)^8} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

We also get the expressions for the first, second, third and fourth order derivatives :

$$\begin{aligned} u_{i+1}' &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}'} - u_i'}{120c_2h} \right) + \left(\frac{120c_2 - 1}{120c_2} \right) u_i' + \left(\frac{240c_2 - 1}{240c_2} \right) hu_i'' + \left(\frac{360c_2 - 1}{720c_2} \right) h^2u_i''' + \left(\frac{480c_2 - 1}{2880c_2} \right) h^3u_i^{IV} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{5c_2 - c_1}{120c_2} \right) h^4u_i^V \\ u_{i+1}'' &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}''} - u_i''}{24c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{24c_1 - 1}{24c_1} \right) u_i'' + \left(\frac{48c_1 - 1}{48c_1} \right) hu_i''' + \left(\frac{72c_1 - 1}{144c_1} \right) h^2u_i^{IV} + \left(\frac{96c_1 - 1}{576c_1} \right) h^3u_i^V \\ u_{i+1}''' &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}'''} - u_i'''}{6c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{6c_1 - 1}{6c_1} \right) u_i''' + \left(\frac{12c_1 - 1}{12c_1} \right) hu_i^{IV} + \left(\frac{18c_1 - 1}{36c_1} \right) h^2u_i^V \\ u_{i+1}^{IV} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}^{IV}} - u_i^{IV}}{2c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{2c_1 - 1}{2c_1} \right) u_i^{IV} + \left(\frac{4c_1 - 1}{4c_1} \right) hu_i^V \end{aligned}$$

where $u_i^V = f_i$.

If R_i denotes the remainder in the approximation at node i , then from above discussion we have $R_i = O(h^7)$.

Therefore, the accuracy of the above method is at least quadratic.

3. Numerical Illustrations

The following six problems illustrate the performance of our method. We compute the maximum absolute errors MAE, MAED1, MAED2, MAED3, MAED4 in the true solutions, its first and second derivatives $u(x), u'(x), u''(x), u'''(x), u^{IV}(x)$ namely :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MAE} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u(x_i) - u_i| \\ \text{MAED1} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u'(x_i) - u'_i| \\ \text{MAED2} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u''(x_i) - u''_i| \\ \text{MAED3} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u'''(x_i) - u'''_i| \\ \text{MAED4} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u^{IV}(x_i) - u^{IV}_i| \end{aligned}$$

All the computations were performed on Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS linux operating system with IDLE 3.8.10 running Python version 3.8.10 on Intel Core[®] i5-9400 CPU @ 2.90GHz × 6 PC.

Example 1. Consider the fifth-order initial value problem :

$$u^V = 24u'u'' + 12(u'')^2 + 12uu''', 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions :

$$u(0) = 1, u'(0) = -2, u''(0) = 6, u'''(0) = -24, u^{IV}(0) = 120$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(1+x)^2}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{3}$ is given below :

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3	MAED4
256	0.0003360262276	0.0014738462695	0.0049064908918	0.0110757259134	0.0128673701558
512	0.0000838470550	0.0003675788778	0.0012230755162	0.0027595519039	0.0032043287472
1024	0.0000209415898	0.0000917836367	0.0003053239845	0.0006887143219	0.0007995192872
2048	0.0000052329726	0.0000229319917	0.0000762741350	0.0001720297157	0.0001996821577

Example 2. Consider the fifth-order initial value problem :

$$u^V = -u'' + 3e^{-x}, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions :

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 1, u''(0) = -2, u'''(0) = 3, u^{IV}(0) = -4$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = xe^{-x}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{3}$ is given below :

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3	MAED4
256	0.0000001236238116	0.0000005980063788	0.0000022759766284	0.0000062820942258	0.0000105928667018
512	0.0000000309543624	0.0000001496682352	0.0000005693911422	0.0000015708522755	0.0000026466875951
1024	0.0000000077755400	0.0000000375367130	0.0000001423393494	0.0000003927730620	0.0000006613501433
2048	0.0000000019907000	0.0000000095395199	0.0000000359836475	0.0000000987956085	0.0000001653049637

Example 3. Consider the fifth-order initial value problem :

$$u^V = 4 \sin x + u', 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions :

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 0, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = 0, u^{IV}(0) = -4$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = x \sin x.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{3}$ is given below :

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3	MAED4
256	0.0000000273127	0.0000001629904	0.0000008069237	0.0000031670012	0.0000091383945
512	0.0000000068702	0.0000000409499	0.0000002025351	0.0000007940414	0.0000022865946
1024	0.0000000016627	0.0000000099750	0.0000000505219	0.0000001985884	0.0000005717037
2048	0.0000000004555	0.0000000026511	0.0000000131022	0.0000000507814	0.0000001440363

Example 4. Consider the fifth-order initial value problem :

$$u^V = 120u^6, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions :

$$u(0) = 1, u'(0) = -1, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = -6, u^{IV}(0) = 24$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{1+x}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{3}$ is given below :

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3	MAED4
256	0.0000452702673	0.0002000882624	0.0006727310940	0.0015396010293	0.0018292304529
512	0.0000113015038	0.0000499262940	0.0001677774953	0.0003837822123	0.0004557469732
1024	0.0000028233293	0.0000124695159	0.0000418931327	0.0000958048208	0.0001137409210
2048	0.0000007058171	0.0000031160780	0.0000104668308	0.0000239337695	0.0000284110890

4. Conclusion

In this paper we have proposed a numerical method to solve fifth order initial value problems having at least quadratic convergence. We have given the derivation for the proposed scheme and estimated the error involved. We have also given several numerical examples which confirms our claim.

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